

Integration of wireless and optical technologies to meet the requirements of 5G networks and beyond

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Abstract—The Centralized Radio Access Network (C-RAN) architecture is necessary to achieve the target goals that have been set for 5G. However, as the number of radio signals to be transported between the Centralized Base Station (CBS) and the Remote Antenna Units (RAUs) grows large, the utilization of contemporary fronthaul technologies (such as CPRI) becomes more difficult. The reason for this is that these Digital Radio-over-Fibre (RoF) solutions were originally designed to be transparent to the transported radio signal, introducing a negligible distortion at the cost of expanding the bandwidth notably and increasing the processing delay. As the assumption of an ideal fronthaul will not be realistic any more for future C-RANs, a novel design paradigm is needed in which the impairments introduced by both fibre fronthaul and wireless air-interface are jointly taken into account. In this contribution, we present our vision about the advantages of using an all-analog fronthaul, identifying potential challenges and proposing possible solutions to address each of them. We claim that the use of low-cost analog components in the RAUs will not only reduce the End-to-End (E2E) latency of the mobile network, but will also enable an ultra-dense deployment of small cells taking advantage of the Passive Optical Network (PON) infrastructure that is already available today in most urban centres.

Keywords—5G and beyond; optical-wireless integration; all-analog fronthaul; centralized processing; low-latency; radio-over-fibre; ultra-dense deployments.

I. INTRODUCTION

The communication network and service environment that are foreseen for year 2020 will be much richer and more complex than the one that has been observed so far in 4G. Among these differences, 5G networks will have to support about 1000 times higher mobile data volume per unit area, 10-100 times more data traffic per user, 10-1000 times higher number of devices, 10 times longer battery life, and 5 times less End-to-End (E2E) latency than today [1]. Trying to address these challenges, the current trend consists in separating the *digital* Baseband Unit (BBU) and *analog* Radio Unit (RU) processing of a traditional Base Station (BS) into two parts, implementing the so-called Centralized Radio Access Network (C-RAN) architecture [2, 3]. A critical part of this architecture is the *fronthaul* network, which connects the Centralized Base Station (CBS) with the Remote Antenna Units (RAUs). To implement it, optical fibres are the natural choice as they introduce low latency and support a large bandwidth [4]. So far, contemporary fronthaul technologies have been designed to be

transparent to the transported radio signals in terms of distortion. Unfortunately, such an idealistic approach will not be practical any more for 5G, as the number of radio signals to be transported between CBS and RAUs will be much larger than today. Due to that, a new fronthaul design paradigm is required, in which the ideal fronthaul requirement is relaxed and the integration of optical and wireless transmissions is jointly optimized.

The prevailing technology that has been used so far to implement the fronthaul of contemporary C-RANs is the Common Public Radio Interface (CPRI) [5]. This technology, which is sometimes referred as Digital Radio-over-Fibre (D-RoF), is based on transmitting digitalized samples of the analog baseband I/Q signals that are generated at the CBS. Unfortunately, a notable bandwidth expansion is experienced over the fibre when using CPRI, as baseband signals need to be oversampled and digitalized with a good resolution to guarantee a negligible distortion [3]. Due to that, a scalability problem emerges when the number of RAUs to be served by the same CBS grows large. Though different approaches can be used to transport the large aggregate data rate that multiple CPRI links create, such as deploying dedicated optical fibres or using different optical wavelengths over the same fibre (WDM – Wavelength Division Multiplexing), all of them imply a modification on the optical network infrastructure that is available today and/or the use of expensive equipment at the RAUs. Moreover, the Digital-to-Analog (D/A) conversion, as well as the error control coding and time-synchronization that is needed to receive the radio signal over CPRI, demand extra hardware complexity (more cost) and additional processing delay (more latency) that complicates the use of CPRI in 5G [6].

On the other hand, the transportation of analog baseband radio signals over the fibre fronthaul has several advantage when compared to digitalized I/Q signal samples [7]. For example, analog Radio-over-Fibre (RoF) does not expand the bandwidth of the information bearing signal, does not introduce processing delay in the fronthaul, and keeps the cost of the RAU at the lowest. However, the main challenge that analog RoF links have is the distortion that the different optical and electrical components of the fronthaul network introduce [8, 9]. In a C-RAN implementation that fulfils 5G requirements, low-cost and small form factor optical transceivers will be needed; therefore, expensive optical amplifiers and high-power consuming elements should be in principle avoided. Fortunately, Passive Optical Networks (PONs) have been extensively deployed in

Figure 1. Illustration of a C-RAN architecture in which all digital and part of the analog signal processing is performed at the CBS. Both fronthaul network and RAUs only contain analog hardware blocks to minimize the network latency. Upstream and downstream transmissions in the fronthaul is done over different wavelengths. Simultaneous transmission of the passband radio signals intended to (coming from) the different RAUs is done over different IF portions of the electrical spectrum. Centralized processing at BBU Pool takes into account the impairments introduced by both optical fronthaul and wireless air interface.

most urban areas to implement the Fibre-to-the-Home (FTTH) access network [10]. Therefore, the most expensive part of the C-RAN architecture, which is also the most time-consuming to fulfil when new fibre deployments are required, is *ready-for-use* in most urban centres today. However, in order to exploit this infrastructure effectively, all the BBU and RU processing that is necessary at both extremes of the PON should be first designed accordingly to deal with the requirements set for 5G networks.

In our proposed *all-analog* mobile fronthaul, the multiple radio signals to be transmitted over the PON will be transported over different Intermediate Frequencies (IFs), each of them occupying an orthogonal portion of the electrical spectrum [11]. After that, the composite electrical signal will modulate the intensity of an optical carrier generated in the CBS. At the RAU, all-analog hardware will be used to detect, filter, and up-convert the passband IF signal to the RF portion of the spectrum in which it should be transmitted over-the-air. As the distance between CBS and RAUs is in the order of few kilometres, the impact of the chromatic dispersion that the Single-Mode Fibre (SMF) introduces will be negligible. Nevertheless, new challenges may arise due to the transportation of a large number of IF subcarriers over the same optical carrier. For example, in the downstream direction, an extremely large Peak-to-Average Power Ratio (PAPR) is expected at the modulator of the Laser Diode (LD) due to the aggregation of a large number of (possibly OFDMA-like) passband signals [12]. Similarly, in the upstream direction, a high Optical Beat Interference (OBI) power is expected at the Photodetector (PD) for receiving non-coherent sources of light modulated in intensity and originated at distributed RAUs [13].

The rest of this report is organized as follows: Section II introduces the system model that integrates the optical fronthaul and wireless air-interface of the C-RAN into a common framework. Section III focuses on the different elements of the all-analog fronthaul that should be used, specifying the most important characteristics to be considered when modelling in each of them. Section IV describes key challenges that were identified to implement the downstream (one-to-many) transmission, whereas Section V extends the analysis to the upstream (many-to-one) direction of communication. Section VI illustrates the proposed C-RAN architecture in detailed, based

on the challenges and key aspects discussed in the previous sections. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section VII.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

The proposed C-RAN architecture is shown in Fig. 1 and can be broadly divided into three different parts, namely a common CBS, a large number of distributed RAUs, and a tree-like optical network that connect the CBS with the distributed RAUs using passive optical splitters/couplers. Bidirectional connectivity between CBS and distributed RAUs is achieved using different wavelengths, namely λ_1 for the downstream and λ_2 for the upstream, respectively. In line with most PON technologies, it is convenient that λ_1 lies in the middle windows of the SMF (*i.e.*, around 1500 nm). For the upstream direction, a sensible choice is to select λ_2 in the lower windows of the SMF (*i.e.*, around 1300 nm). An optical circulator is used at both extremes of the fronthaul link to make the optical carriers travel in the correct direction of communication.

Apart from the digital BBUs and analog RUs, the CBS also contains the Optical Line Terminal (OLT). In the downstream, the OLT is in charge of multiplexing the passband radio signals associated to the different RAUs on different IFs and, after that, perform the Electrical-to-Optical (E/O) conversion that is necessary to inject the composite signal into the feeder link of the PON. At the other extreme of the fronthaul, there is an Optical Network Unit (ONUs) in each RAU. The ONU is in charge of performing the Optical-to-Electrical (O/E) conversion, extracting the analog passband signal that is located around the IF that corresponds to the RAU, and up-converting it to the Radio Frequency (RF) band before its final transmission over the downlink air interface.

The opposite situation takes place in the upstream, where the ONUs down-convert the uplink RF signal that is received from the Mobile Stations (MSs) into the IF portion that corresponds to each RAU and, after that, performs the E/O conversion that is necessary to transport it over the PON towards the OLT. At the OLT, the composite upstream optical signal is first O/E converted and, then, it is divided into different

IF bands such that the appropriate passband radio signal is fed in the RU (*i.e.*, receiver frontend) and BBU that is in charge of processing the signal received by the target RAU.

Finally, it is important to highlight that all digital signal processing in the proposed C-RAN architecture is performed at the CBS. Therefore, as Channel State Information (CSI) and data symbols addressed to (coming from) the different MS in the C-RAN can be collected at a common place, advanced cooperative transmission schemes can be easily implemented to maximize the data rate performance that, *e.g.*, a cluster of RAUs can provide to a set of MSs that are located in the same coverage area. Moreover, as RAUs take the role of Amplify-and-Forward (AF) relays, the signal that is transmitted over the hybrid optical-wireless transmission medium that is configured can be jointly optimized to address the impairments introduced by both optical fronthaul and wireless air-interface segments.

III. ELEMENTS OF THE ALL-ANALOG FRONTHAUL NETWORK

In this section we present the different elements of the all-analog fronthaul network that has been proposed, specifying their characteristics as well as the most critical aspects that should be considered when modelling each of them within the proposed C-RAN architecture.

A. Electrical-to-Optical Conversion

The easiest way to modulate the intensity of the light emitted by a LD consists in controlling its driving current. Though this *direct modulation* of a LD is simple to implement, its practical utilization pose several challenging problems. For example, the physical mechanisms that are used in the LD to obtain the desired intensity modulation of the optical signal generate as secondary effect an *undesired* phase modulation. This latter effect, which is known as *frequency chirp* [9, 14], expands the power spectrum of the optical signal at the output of the LD. Since different frequency components travel at different speeds inside the optical fibre, the frequency chirp broadens the optical pulses that are transmitted. Due to that, the energy of adjacent optical pulses start to overlap in time and, as result, Inter-Symbol Interference (ISI) power becomes stronger and stronger as transmission distance grows. Another challenge of direct modulation is the limited modulation bandwidth that can be supported by the LD, which is usually in the order of few GHz at the very best for most practical cases [11].

Apart from direct modulation, the intensity of the light emitted by a LD can also be controlled with an external device that changes the amount of optical power that goes through it according to the voltage that is applied in its control inputs [15]. In general terms, external modulators can be broadly classified into two different types: Electro-Absorption Modulator (EAM) and Mach-Zehnder Modulator (MZM). In the EAM, the percentage of photons that is absorbed when travelling in the optical waveguide inside the device is modulated by the varying strength of the electrical field that is applied across the waveguide. In the MZM, the phase of the light in the optical waveguide is modulated and, then, converted to intensity modulation by combining the phase-modulated light in the second path of the Mach-Zehnder interferometer. When compared to direct modulation, external modulation does not suffer from (notable) frequency chirp and provides a

modulation bandwidth that is typically an order of magnitude higher than the one obtained with direct modulation.

1) *Intensity Modulation System*: The characteristic transfer function of a MZM is given by [16]

$$\frac{P_{out}}{P_{in}} = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \cos \left(\frac{\pi V_{in}}{V_{\pi}} \right) \right] = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \cos \left(\frac{\pi (V_B + v_m)}{V_{\pi}} \right) \right], \quad (1)$$

where P_{out} and P_{in} are the output and input optical power, respectively, V_{π} is the half-wave voltage of the MZM, and V_{in} is the modulation voltage that is applied at the control terminals. The input voltage can be further divided into two terms, namely bias voltage V_B and modulating signal v_m . Therefore, if we apply a bias voltage equal to $V_B = nV_{\pi}/2$ for odd values of n ,

$$\frac{P_{out}(t)}{P_{in}} = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 \mp \sin \left(\frac{\pi v_m(t)}{V_{\pi}} \right) \right] \approx \frac{1}{2} \left[1 \mp \frac{\pi v_m(t)}{V_{\pi}} \right] \quad n = 1, 3, \dots \quad (2)$$

results, where the latter approximation is valid when the modulating signal component is in the small signal regime (*i.e.*, when $v_m(t) \ll V_{\pi}$). Therefore, if we use an appropriate bias point, such as $V_B = 3V_{\pi}/2$, equation (2) attains the form

$$P_{out}(t) = \frac{P_{in}}{2} [1 + \beta v_m(t)], \quad (3)$$

where $\beta = \pi/V_{\pi}$ is the intensity modulation index. Equation (2) can also be re-written as function of the electric field and, using the first-order Taylor series expansion of $\sqrt[3]{1+x} \approx 1+x/2$ when $x \ll 1$, the output electric field becomes

$$E_{out}(t) \approx |E_{in}| e^{j(\omega t + \phi)} \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \left[1 \mp \frac{\pi v_m(t)}{2V_{\pi}} \right]} \quad n = 1, 3, \dots \quad (4)$$

where ω and ϕ are the angular frequency and phase of the light emitted by the LD. If we re-write (4) considering $V_B = 3V_{\pi}/2$,

$$E_{out}(t) \approx A [1 + \alpha v_m(t)] e^{j(\omega t + \phi)} \quad (5)$$

results, where $A = |E_{in}|/\sqrt{2}$ and $\alpha = \pi/(2V_{\pi})$ are the amplitude and electrical modulation index, respectively. It is worth noticing that when the modulating signal $v_m(t)$ is zero, the intensity of the output optical signal is half the intensity of the one applied at the input of the MZM. The presence of the optical carrier at the output of the modulator makes this signal suitable to be directly-detected with a PD (incoherent receiver).

2) *Electric-field Modulation System*: On the other hand, when the bias voltage is an odd multiple of the half-wave voltage, such as *e.g.* $V_B = V_{\pi}$, the optical power intensity at the output of the MZM is given by

$$P_{out}(t) = \frac{P_{in}}{2} \left[1 - \cos \left(\frac{\pi v_m(t)}{V_{\pi}} \right) \right] \approx \frac{P_{in}}{2} \left(\frac{\pi v_m(t)}{V_{\pi}} \right)^2, \quad (6)$$

where the latter approximation is valid when the modulating signal is in the small signal regime (*i.e.*, when $v_m(t) \ll V_{\pi}$). In this situation, the corresponding output electrical field becomes

$$E_{out}(t) \approx |E_{in}| e^{j(\omega t + \phi)} \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\pi v_m(t)}{V_{\pi}} \right) = \alpha A v_m(t) e^{j(\omega t + \phi)}, \quad (7)$$

Figure 2. Illustration of a PON with multiple levels of passive power splitters (downstream)/couplers (upstream). In the proposed C-RAN, the OLT should be located in the CBS and there should be one ONU per RAU.

where $A = |E_{in}|$ and $\alpha = \pi/(2V_{\pi})$ are the amplitude and electrical modulation index, respectively. When comparing (5) with (7), it is possible to see that the electrical modulation index remains the same, whereas the presence of the optical carrier at the output of the MZM has been suppressed in the latter case. This scheme is known as *linear field modulation*, and demands heterodyne detection in reception as there is no optical carrier reference to use a direct-detection scheme with a PD. Due to that, a coherent receiver architecture is needed [17], increasing the complexity of the system at both optical link extremes.

B. Passive Optical Network

Recently, PONs have been widely deployed to provide low-cost, high-capacity, and high-flexibility *last mile* broadband access to individual end-users. The key feature of a PON is the point-to-multipoint architecture that it has, which is implemented in practice using passive optical splitters/couplers that enable the tree-like topology that is needed to connect multiple end-users with a single optical fibre. The typical split ratio of a PON is 64, the conventional coverage range is about 20 km (max. 60 km), and the maximum link loss budget is typically in the order of 30 dB [8].

The architecture of the PON that is considered in this contribution is presented in Fig. 2. The topology contains an OLT and multiple ONUs. A single fibre link, known as feeder link, connects the OLT to the intermediate optical power splitter/coupler of the PON. In practice, this is usually implemented by using primary and secondary splitting/coupling stages, which are usually located near the OLT and the ONUs, respectively. This way, up to N ONUs can be connected using a single-fibre optical network with a tree-like topology.

Since the maximum reach of an access PON is typically in the order of 20 km, the non-linear effects of fibre that are typically considered to model the achievable data rate in long-haul fibre optic networks can be ignored [18]. Moreover, as PONs do not use optical amplifiers in the external plant, the degradation of the optical SNR caused by the Amplified Spontaneous Emission (ASE) noises can be also neglected. Finally, the Chromatic Dispersion (CD) that a SMF introduces in a short-reach PON will be low [9]; due to that, the frequency-response of the equivalent electrical channel will be practically flat within the modulation bandwidth of the external modulator. To sum up, the only effects that play a key role when modelling the response of the PON are the attenuation of the SMF (L_f) and the splitting factor of the optical power splitters/couplers (L_s). In

this report, the effects of the Rayleigh Backscattering are neglected as there are techniques reported in the literature that can be used to control this impairment successfully.

C. Optical-to-Electrical Conversion

The O/E conversion in a direct-detected system is performed using a PD. The unfiltered electrical current at the PD output follows the square-law detection principle [19], which is mathematically modelled as

$$I_{pd}(t) = \mu |E_{pd}(t)|^2 = \mu E_{pd}(t) E_{pd}(t)^*, \quad (8)$$

where $|E_{pd}| = |E_{out}|/\sqrt{L_f L_s}$ is the module of the electrical field at the input of the PD, whereas μ [A/W] is the responsivity of the PD. Therefore, when the bias voltage of the MZM is selected such that the Intensity Modulation of the LD light given in (5) is achieved, the current at the output of the PD is given by

$$I_{pd}(t) = \mu \frac{A^2}{L_f L_s} [1 + \alpha v_m(t)]^2 \approx \mu [A_{pd}^2 + 2A_{pd}^2 \alpha v_m(t)], \quad (9)$$

where $A_{pd} = \sqrt{A^2/(L_f L_s)}$ is the amplitude of the electrical field at the input of the PD. It is worth noticing that the latter approximation in (9) results when $\alpha v_m(t) \ll 1$, such that the MZM operates in its linear-response region (*i.e.*, when input signal is in small regime). In most practical cases, the bandwidth of the PD is larger than the bandwidth of the external modulator. Therefore, the electrical modulation bandwidth of the IF-aggregated signal that is transported over the optical fronthaul will be mainly limited by the 3-dB bandwidth that the MZM has.

IV. CHALLENGES IN THE DOWNSTREAM TRANSMISSION

In this section we describe briefly two of the key challenges that have been identified in the downstream direction, namely PAPR re-growth and joint optimization of the optical-wireless transmission link that is configured in the C-RAN fronthaul. For the sake of brevity, we do not explain in detail here the effect of other problems that may be found in the downstream direction, such as the impact of adjacent channel interference and the management of communication resources when optical-wireless link response is taken into account.

A. Peak-to-Average Power Ratio

In an Intensity Modulation Direct Detection (IM/DD) optical system, the intensity of the optical carrier should be modulated according to the instantaneous value of the passband electrical signal that wants to be transmitted. Therefore, any OFDM-based solution that verifies the requirements of optical systems should provide as output a signal that is unipolar in nature, as the intensity of an optical signal can only take *real* and *positive* values [20]. In practice, this requirement is achieved by imposing the *Hermitian* symmetry condition on the data vector that is fed into each Inverse Fast Fourier Transform (IFFT) block of the transmitter. This way, an output electrical signal that is real and bipolar is obtained; the cost to be paid is the utilization of only half of the electrical subcarriers to

Figure 3. PAPR re-growth effect that is experienced after combining few independent OFDM-based signals, which are addressed to different RAUs but need to be transmitted over the same optical carrier in the downstream.

transport information. The unipolarity of the obtained real signal can be achieved adding a DC level to the electrical signal that modulates the intensity of the light emitted by the LD. This scheme is known as DC-biased Optical OFDM (DCO-OFDM), and the selection of the most convenient level of DC is a non-trivial optimization task that should also be performed [21, 22].

One of the key challenges of OFDM-based signals is the high PAPR that is obtained when the phases of different subcarriers combine constructively at the IFFT output. The Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of the PAPR depends mainly on the number of subcarriers (IFFT-size) of the composite OFDM signal [23]. It is interesting to note that the modulation format that is used per subcarrier does not have a notable effect on the PAPR that is experienced. One simple way to keep the PAPR under control consists in clipping the value of the output signal when it exceeds a given threshold. However, since clipping introduces in-band distortion that reduces the quality of the desired signal, as well as out-of-band distortion that affects the signal on neighbouring channels, it is convenient to keep its probability of occurrence under control [20, 24]. So far, this has been studied for contemporary wireless communication systems, where the trade-off between Input Power Backoff (IBO) and PAPR probability has been characterized in detail in many publications [25].

Unfortunately, when transporting multiple electrical OFDM-based signals over the same IM/DD optical fibre link, a PAPR re-growth effect is experienced [12]. This effect, which is illustrated in Fig. 3, implies that a large PAPR may be experienced in the composite signal that is injected into the E/O converter of the CBS even when the PAPR of each individual signal that enters the Multiplexer is individually kept under control. Therefore, a joint optimization of the clipping thresholds at both individual component signals (output of IFFT blocks) and composite aggregate signal (input of E/O converter) must be studied, such that the impairments introduced in the all-analog fronthaul can be jointly controlled.

B. Achievable Data Rate of Hybrid Optical-Wireless Link

Traditionally, the modulation and coding scheme that a wireless communication system utilizes depends on the channel gains that are experienced in the wireless (radio) channel. However, when the optical fronthaul network is not ideal any

Figure 4. Upper panel: Joint optimization of the modulation and coding scheme to maximize the E2E data rate of the hybrid optical-wireless link that is configured in the proposed C-RAN architecture. Lower Panel: Equivalent AF Relay System that is configured in the fronthaul link.

more, the achievable data rate should also take into account the effect that the fronthaul link has on the E2E data rate. That is, the hybrid optical-wireless link that is configured when the optical fronthaul is cascaded with the wireless air-interface becomes an AF relaying system, where the first link is a real Intensity-Modulated Channel and the second link is a complex AWGN linear channel, as illustrated in Fig. 4. A similar concept has been studied in [26] for a hybrid system that combines Power Line Communications (PLC) and Visible Light Communications (VLC) in the first and second hop of an equivalent AF system, respectively. Nevertheless, in the optical-wireless case, certain modifications are required to maximize the achievable E2E data rate from a more theoretical perspective [27].

As expected, the joint optimization of the signal transported over the hybrid optical-wireless link (*i.e.*, first and second hops) will provide a better E2E data rate, when compared to the one that would be obtained when the optimization of the transported signal considers the impairments introduced in the wireless link only (*i.e.*, first hop). It is worth noticing that this has been the predominant approach considered so far, where the design of the fronthaul solution (*e.g.*, CPRI) has set as requirement that the distortion introduced by the optical fibre link on the transported radio signal should be negligible [3, 5].

V. CHALLENGES IN THE UPSTREAM TRANSMISSION

As previously mentioned, the design of an upstream transmission architecture using a single optical wavelength is much more challenging than the one needed for the equivalent downstream counterpart. Though there are many challenges that could be listed, in this section we briefly describe two of them, namely Optical Intermodulation Distortion and Near-Far Effect. In both cases, the problem arises for the distributed nature of RAUs, which makes the many-to-one transmission in the upstream more challenging than the one-to-many transmission in the downstream. In order to keep the PAPR under control, a SC-FDM modulation scheme is expected to be utilized over each electrical signal that is generated at each RAU [23]. The modulation of a common seed light emitted by the CBS can also be achieved using a Reflective Semiconductor Optical Amplifier (RSOA), whose modulation bandwidth is typical in the order of few GHz [18]. However, in this paper we

focus on a more traditional assumption, in which the seed light is recovered at each RAU using an optical filter and, after its amplification, it is modulated by an external modulator [13, 28].

A. Optical Inter-Modulation Distortion

One of the key challenges in the upstream transmission is the OBI, which is created in the PD due to the superposition of incoherent sources of light that are independently modulated in intensity. This effect takes place in presence of both distributed light sources (*i.e.*, one LD per RAU) and centralized light sources (*i.e.*, one common LD at the CBS) [13]. In the distributed case, which is the upstream architecture used in TDM-based 10G-PON and 10GE-PON, there is one LD per RAU. Unfortunately, as it will be shown below, this approach cannot be easily extended to the all-analog fronthaul architecture that we propose. In the centralized case, there is a LD at the CBS that provide a common *light seed* to all RAUs. Though the OBI problem will be present in both cases, we will soon show that the negative impact is higher in the distributed LD architecture than in the centralized LD one.

1) *Upstream transmission with distributed LDs:* For illustrative purposes, let us start characterizing the OBI problem in presence of two distributed light sources. As the analysis presented here is generalized in nature, it can be easily extended later on to a larger number of RAUs if desired.

When $N = 2$, the total electrical field at the PD input is

$$\begin{aligned} E_{pd,tot}(t) &= E_{pd,1}(t) + E_{pd,2}(t) \\ &= A_{pd,1} [1 + \alpha_1 v_{m,1}(t)] e^{j(\omega_1 t + \phi_1)} + A_{pd,2} [1 + \alpha_2 v_{m,2}(t)] e^{j(\omega_2 t + \phi_2)}, \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where $A_{pd,1}$ and $A_{pd,2}$ are the amplitude of the electrical field coming from RAU 1 and RAU 2, respectively. Similarly, α_1 and α_2 are the intensity modulation indexes that are used to modulate the optical carriers with $v_{m,1}(t)$ and $v_{m,2}(t)$ at RAU 1 and RAU 2, respectively. Then, the current at the PD output when both external modulators operate in their linear region (*i.e.*, when $|\alpha_1 v_{m,1}(t)| \ll 1$ and $|\alpha_2 v_{m,2}(t)| \ll 1$) is given by

$$\begin{aligned} I_{pd,tot}(t) &= \mu |E_{pd,tot}(t)|^2 = \mu E_{pd,tot}(t) E_{pd,tot}^*(t) \\ &= \mu A_{pd,1}^2 [1 + \alpha_1 v_{m,1}(t)]^2 + \mu A_{pd,2}^2 [1 + \alpha_2 v_{m,2}(t)]^2 \\ &\quad + 2\mu A_{pd,1} A_{pd,2} [1 + \alpha_1 v_{m,1}(t)] [1 + \alpha_2 v_{m,2}(t)] \Re\{e^{j(\omega_1 t + \phi_1)} e^{-j(\omega_2 t + \phi_2)}\} \\ &\approx \mu (A_{pd,1}^2 + A_{pd,2}^2) + 2\mu (A_{pd,1}^2 \alpha_1 v_{m,1}(t) + A_{pd,2}^2 \alpha_2 v_{m,2}(t)) \\ &\quad + 2\mu A_{pd,1} A_{pd,2} [1 + \alpha_1 v_{m,1}(t) + \alpha_2 v_{m,2}(t)] \cos(\Delta\omega t + \Delta\phi), \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where $\Delta\omega = \omega_1 - \omega_2$ and $\Delta\phi = \phi_1 - \phi_2$ are the angular frequency offset and phase noise between the optical carriers of RAU 1 and RAU 2, respectively. When we focus in the last approximation of (11), it is possible to see that the first term is a DC level, the second term contains the desired composite signal that wants to be transmitted in the upstream direction, and the third term represents the OBI that is generated at the PD and is difficult to manage when free-running LDs are used. In most practical situations, the angular frequency difference

between the LDs of both RAUs may vary notably, even when they have the same nominal wavelength. As the frequency offset is typically unstable and may change drastically from time to time (*e.g.*, due to the variability in the temperature that each LD experiences), the resulting OBI is difficult to control. This effect deteriorates notably the quality of the received signal at the output of the PD, limiting the applicability of distributed LDs to implement the upstream transmission in a C-RAN architecture that relies on an all-analog fronthaul.

2) *Upstream transmission with centralized LDs:* One simple option to reduce the impact of OBI consists in deploying a centralized LD at the premises of the CBS, and distribute this common light source to the different optical modulators that are located in each RAU. In this case, the frequency offset of the modulated light sources coming from the distributed RAUs will be the same (*i.e.*, $\Delta\omega = 0$). However, the phase noise generated by the incoherent light sources will affect the spectrum of the received signal when a traditional IM/DD system is used, *i.e.*,

$$\begin{aligned} I_{pd,tot}(t) &\approx \mu (A_{pd,1}^2 + A_{pd,2}^2) \\ &\quad + 2\mu (A_{pd,1}^2 \alpha_1 v_{m,1}(t) + A_{pd,2}^2 \alpha_2 v_{m,2}(t)) \\ &\quad + 2\mu A_{pd,1} A_{pd,2} [1 + \alpha_1 v_{m,1}(t) + \alpha_2 v_{m,2}(t)] \cos(\Delta\phi) \\ &= \mu [A_{pd,1}^2 + A_{pd,2}^2 + 2A_{pd,1} A_{pd,2} \cos(\Delta\phi)] \\ &\quad + 2\mu \alpha_1 A_{pd,1} [A_{pd,1} + A_{pd,2} \cos(\Delta\phi)] v_{m,1}(t) \\ &\quad + 2\mu \alpha_2 A_{pd,2} [A_{pd,2} + A_{pd,1} \cos(\Delta\phi)] v_{m,2}(t), \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where the three terms in the second equality are a DC level, the desired signal coming from RAU 1, and the desired signal coming from RAU 2. It is important to note that the desired signal coming from the different RAUs will be scaled by a factor that depends not only on the phase noise $\Delta\phi$, but also on the amplitudes of the electrical field that is received from each of the RAUs that utilize the same upstream wavelength (*i.e.*, λ_2). Since this scaling factor is very difficult to control in practice, we can assume that it takes a *random* but constant value during a transmission time interval with duration to be defined. Later on, the value of this scaling factor can be stochastically modelled, such that the centralized processing that is performed at the CBS takes into account its probabilistic behaviour in order to optimize the E2E data rate that the proposed C-RAN architecture would be able to provide.

B. Near-far effect in the Upstream

In the upstream direction of communication, the data stream that is generated by the different MS is not synchronized. Due to that, intra-cell interference occurs when the transmission of different MSs are scheduled in adjacent portions of the RF band. One simple way to keep this impairment under control consists in applying open loop power control in uplink, such that the received power per subcarrier at the BS antenna is the same for all MSs [29]. This way, the intra-cell interference in uplink is kept under control, regardless the distance the each MS has towards the serving BS.

Figure 5. Illustration of a C-RAN with all-analog fronthaul on different optical wavelengths in downstream (λ_1) and upstream (λ_2). Radio carrier multiplexing over the same optical wavelength takes place using FDM over different IFs. Acronyms used in this figure: **BB**: Baseband signal. **IF**: Intermediate Frequency signal. **RF**: Radio Frequency. **LD**: Laser Diode. **PD**: Photodetector. **MUX**: Multiplexer. **DEMUX**: Demultiplexer.

In the proposed C-RAN architecture, the uplink power control that is applied at the MSs should take into account the combined effect of the optical-wireless link that is configured. In principle, the transmission power that each MS applies should compensate the mean path loss attenuation that is experienced. In practice, this value can be estimated in downlink, using for this purpose the received power of the reference signals that are transported in the downstream. However, the effect that different optical power have in the resulting OBI should be also considered, as it affects not only the received signal quality of the reference signal, but also the received signal quality of the signals that are transported on the adjacent IF channels that correspond to the same optical carrier.

VI. PROPOSED C-RAN TO FULFIL 5G REQUIREMENTS

Figure 5 summarizes the C-RAN architecture that has been proposed to fulfil the requirements of 5G networks. An all-analog fronthaul has been considered, with a centralized processing that takes into account the impairments introduced by both optical and wireless segments of the C-RAN.

A. Downstream transmission

The passband radio signal that each RAU transmits in downlink is first generated in the corresponding BBU and, after that, it is D/A converted before the RF frontend (transmitter). The simultaneous transportation of multiple passband radio signals over a single optical carrier is achieved using an FDM approach, where multiple IFs with a proper separation are used to transport the radio signal associated to each of the distributed RAUs. Then, the composite electrical signal that is created after multiplexing the different IFs is used to modulate in intensity of the optical carrier that corresponds to the downstream LD. This is achieved with the aid of an external modulator, to keep the frequency chirp under control. In Fig. 5, the downstream

transmission takes place around wavelength λ_1 , and the external modulator is a MZM.

At the RAU side, an optical filter is first used to extract the energy of the optical signal that corresponds to the downstream transmission. Then, a PD that converts the received optical power into an electrical current signal is used for direct detection. After that, the aggregate electrical signal is passband filtered around the corresponding IF, before its up-conversion to the RF band in which it should be finally transmitted wirelessly from the RAU antenna towards the target MS.

B. Upstream transmission

The RF signal that comes from each MS is first down-converted to the corresponding IF and, after that, it is used to modulate in intensity the optical carrier that corresponds to the upstream. Unfortunately, the use of separate free-running LDs at the RAUs creates strong OBI if direct-detection is used at the CBS. The reason for this is that the instantaneous frequency and phase of independent LDs vary notably in practice and, due to that, the spectra of the received signals will overlap even when LDs have the same nominal wavelength. To prevent this problem, we assume that the upstream optical carrier is first generated in the CBS and, then, distributed to the different RAUs over the PON. This way, each RAU is able to recover the upstream optical carrier with the aid of a passband optical filter centred at λ_2 and, after that, amplify and modulate in intensity the same optical carrier using as modulating message the IF passband signal that corresponds to the RAU. Though optical carriers in the upstream will now have the same instantaneous frequency, the instantaneous phase may change. By the proper selection of the MZM bias voltage, an electric-field modulation scheme with carrier suppression can be achieved; this way, all the optical power that is transmitted in the upstream can be used to transport the information symbols that come from the MSs.

At the receiver side of the upstream, the optical reference carrier with wavelength λ_2 is first coupled to the received optical signal and, after that, a PD is used for direct detection. Finally, electrical filters, down-conversion, and Analog-to-Digital (A/D) conversion are utilized to obtain each of the digital BB signals that are needed at each BBU block.

VII. CONCLUSION

The integration of optical and wireless transmissions will be critical to achieve the target goals that have been set for 5G. In practice, this implies a very large number of small cells that coordinate their transmissions jointly, without incurring on high processing delay and without demanding excessive costs. From our perspective, the use of a novel C-RAN architecture that implements centralized processing and transports the radio signals over an *all-analog* fronthaul has notable advantages when compared to other solutions considered so far, in which the splitting between the CBS and RAU functions is done at a higher layer level of the protocol stack. In our proposed C-RAN architecture, processing delay and RAU cost is kept to a minimum as only analog hardware is needed in the fronthaul. Moreover, the centralized processing that is performed at the BBU pool can take into account the impairments introduced by the hybrid optical-wireless link that emerges when the ideal fronthaul requirement considered nowadays is relaxed. Different challenges that appear when implementing the upstream and downstream have been identified, along with possible approaches that could be used to tackle each of them effectively while keeping implementation complexity low.

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